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Annex C Survey

The aim of this survey is to collect information on implementation of measures to mitigate the risk of introduction of VHSV, IHNV and HPR-deleted ISAV including practical experiences, best practices or practical difficulties.

Please when answering the survey, consider that these measures specifically concern establishments where fertilised eggs and/or gametes are produced or received.

A. GENERAL INFORMATION

1. Type of establishments you work for:

(more than one answer is possible)

- Private company
- Private field veterinarian
- Competent Authority
- Other → Please specify: free text response

2. Please indicate the Country/ies where you are operating:

Free text response

3. Please indicate the fish species reared in the establishment(s) you visit:

(more than one answer is possible)

- Atlantic salmon → Please indicate how many Atlantic salmon establishments: box with number form
- Rainbow trout → please indicate how many Rainbow trout establishments: box with number form

4. Is the establishment(s) you work with a provider of eyed eggs and or receiver of eyed eggs

- Yes, they are provider(s) → Please indicate how many provider establishments: box with number
- Yes, they are receiver(s) → Please indicate how many receiver establishments: box with number
- None is provider nor receiver
- Not applicable
- Other please specify: free text response

5. How many fish establishments, which are not receiver or provider, are you serving?

Free text response

6. In the establishment(s) you visit do Atlantic salmon broodstock have a sea water phase in open pens?

- Yes, all
- Yes, some of them
- None of them
- other → Please specify: free text response
- Not applicable

7. In the establishment(s) you visit: do rainbow trout broodstock have a sea water phase in open pens?

- Yes, al
- Yes, some of them
- None of them
- Other → Please specify: free text response
- Not applicable

8. Please indicate if the establishment you work with trades eggs with providers/receivers of eggs and their health status:

(more than one answer is possible)

- A provider to the same or lower health status establishment within the Country
- A provider to the same or lower health status establishment outside the Country
- A receiver from the same or higher health status establishment within the Country
- A receiver from the same or higher health status establishment outside the Country
- Other → Please specify: free text response

9. Is any of the establishment(s) you work with or the zones/compartments they belong to, officially free from any of those:

(more than one answer is possible)

- Officially free from VHSV → Please indicate how many are VHSV officially free out of the number of farm(s) you visit
- Officially free from IHNV → Please indicate how many are IHNV officially free out of the number of farm(s) you visit
- Officially free from HPR-deleted ISAV → Please indicate how many are HPR-deleted ISAV officially free out of the number of farm(s) you visit

For the establishment(s) you visit, please answer the following questions and describe and explain any difference among establishments

B. TESTING OF BROODSTOCK

Part B was repeated for broodstock fish that stay their entire life in fresh water (F) and for broodstock fish that stay part of their life in seawater (S)

(F) (S) 1. Individual testing at stripping

Are broodfish sampled at stripping for testing for any of those viruses? (question repeated for: VHSV, IHNV, HPR-deleted ISAV)

- No
- Yes, and every fish tested
- Yes, but only a subset of them is tested

Please specify if your answer varies among establishments and explain (e.g. according to scale of production, to the historical health status related to those three pathogens, being in an officially disease-free zone/compartments, etc etc...): free text response

Are the samples from different individuals pooled at the testing phase? Pooled up to 10 for IHNV and VHSV, and up to 5 for HPR-deleted ISAV (question repeated for: VHSV, IHNV, HPR-deleted ISAV)

- Yes
- No

Please feel free to add a comment: free text response

What type of sample is used for testing?

(more than answer is possible)

- Internal organs
- Ovarian fluids
- Others → Please specify: free text response

Could you please list points where major bottlenecks, difficulties or common failures are encountered when implementing individual testing of broodfish? Please also describe and explain any difference among establishments: free text response

(F) (S) 2. Population testing

Is a sample of the fish population tested in the establishment to assess the health status during production of the broodstock? (question repeated for: VHSV, IHNV, HPR-deleted ISAV)

- Yes
- No

What is the sampling size and the frequency of the sampling? (question repeated for: VHSV, IHNV, HPR-deleted ISAV) Please specify if your answer varies among establishments and explain (e.g. according to scale of production, to the historical health status related to those three pathogens, being in an officially disease-free zone/compartment, etc...): free text response

Could you please list points where major bottlenecks, difficulties or common failures are encountered when implementing population testing. Please also describe and explain any differences among establishments: free text response

(F) (S) 3. Re-use of broodfish after stripping

Is the broodfish re-used for reproduction after stripping?

- Yes
- No

Please also describe and explain any difference among establishments: free text response

C. DISINFECTION OF EGGS

(P) Disinfection of eggs at the origin (producer establishment)

(P) 1. Is disinfection with iodine applied to eggs?

- Yes, to all the produced eggs
- Yes, to a part of the produced eggs → Please explain why disinfection is applied to only a part of the eggs: free text response

If no, please explain why disinfection is not applied: free text response

Please also describe and explain any difference among and within establishments: free text response

(P) 2. At which stages is disinfection applied?

(more than one answer is possible)

- Green eggs
- Eyed eggs

Is disinfection applied once or more than once?

- Once → Please explain why only once: free text response
- More than once → Please explain at which stage (eyed or green eggs) and how often: free text response

(P) 3. Do you use the eggs disinfection protocol recommended by WOA?

- Yes, in all farms
- Yes, but not in all farms → Please indicate which one you use: free text response
- No, in any of the farms → Please explain and indicate which protocol you use: free text response

(P) 4. Do you see any weakness/impracticalities/losses/side effects in the disinfection protocol recommended by WOA (e.g. minimum time)?

Free text response

(R) Disinfection of eggs at the destination (receiver establishment)

(R) 1. Is disinfection with iodine applied to eggs at destination?

- Yes, to all the produced eggs
- Yes, to a part of the produced eggs → please explain why disinfection is applied to only a part of the eggs: free text response
- No → Please explain why disinfection is not applied: free text response

(R) 2. Do you use the eggs disinfection protocol recommended by WOA?

- Yes, in all farms
- Yes, but not in all farms → Please indicate which one you use: free text response
- No, in any of the farms → Please explain and indicate which protocol you use: free text response

(R) 3. Do you see any weakness/impracticalities/losses/side effects in the disinfection protocol recommended by WOA (e.g. minimum time)?

Free text response

(M) Disinfection of milt

In case of importation of frozen milt, in your opinion would it be feasible to apply disinfection to fertilised eggs after using the imported milt? Please explain: free text response

D. CRITICAL POINTS

In order to mitigate the risk of introduction of VHSV, IHNV and HPR-deleted ISAV, please add your note/comments on major bottlenecks for implementation, difficulties in adoption, common failures or best practices for each of the critical points listed in Table C.1. Note that Table C.1 in Annex C corresponds to Table 10 in the scientific opinion.

TABLE C.1 Critical points which could be controlled at the establishments where the fertilised eggs and gametes of aquaculture animals are produced, to avoid the spread of ISAV, IHNV and VHSV and ensure early detection if they occur.

Critical points	Description of biosecurity and management practices which could positively affect the critical point	Please add your note/comments on major bottlenecks for implementation,
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		difficulties in adoption, common failures
<i>Health and surveillance</i>		
Systematic control of the health status of the population in the establishment producing eggs/gametes	<p>Dead and moribund fish collected daily and tested for ISAV, IHNV and VHSV upon suspicion. Targeted sampling regularly conducted following predetermined plans for laboratory examinations.</p> <p>Regular visits by fish health personnel (Competent Authority or accredited by them) during the growth of brood fish. The health visits must be planned and carried out based on an assessment of the risk of introduction of infection into the facility, development of disease and spread of infection from the facility. Factors that should be considered when scheduling relevant health visits and sampling include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • increased unexplained mortality • clinical signs and necroscopy findings • abnormal behaviour • reduced feed intake • movement of fish into or out of the facility • knowledge of recent disease history at the establishment and in neighbouring farms (e.g. 5 or 10 km radius zones) or at all farms located upstream in the watercourse. <p>The presence of any of the aforementioned factors should initiate suspicion or rather trigger further investigation</p>	(free text note/comment)
Clinical surveillance	In the event of unexplained increased mortality or other signs of disease (in any of the fish populations in the establishment, including the larvae/fish from imported eggs/gametes), the competent authority or health personnel accredited by them should be informed and carry out health visits followed up with testing for the presence of VHSV, IHNV and HPR-deleted ISAV.	(free text note/comment)
Testing of broodstock	Testing of broodstock for IHNV, VHSV and/or HPR-deleted ISAV is conducted by targeted sampling in connection with regular clinical inspections of the fish. Inspections and samplings are done by the competent authorities or personnel approved for this. Testing only to be conducted by laboratories approved by the competent authorities.	(free text note/comment)

	In addition, broodstock or part of these are tested individually for HPR-deleted ISAV, IHNV and/or VHSV, following stripping.	
Compliance with reporting obligations	Any suspicions/positive tests for VHSV, IHNV and/or HPR-deleted ISAV must be reported to the competent authorities	(free text note/comment)
<i>Establishment (egg-producing)</i>		
Water source	<p>In production systems with an open seawater phase: The distance between the establishment where the fish that are intended to become broodstock are kept and other establishments with salmonids should be known. No specific minimum distance is specified, but the information on the proximity to other establishments with salmonids should be included in the risk assessment in the event of importation.</p> <p>In production systems with fresh water only: Inlet water should be from sources free from the pathogens in question (i.e. borehole water or surface water that does not have anadromous wild fish populations or, for fish farms located upstream in the watercourse, their health status should be free from those infections). Alternatively, removal of particles by filtration and disinfection by ultraviolet treatment and/or ozone is necessary, with the functional requirements of inactivating the agents in question.</p>	(free text note/comment)
Time since last outbreak of the diseases in question at the establishment and in the neighbouring area	Eradication procedure, duration of quarantine period following the last outbreak must be documented. The time since the last outbreak should be documented and will be used as part of the risk assessment for importing.	(free text note/comment)
Water flow within the establishment	In facilities where both eggs and grow-out fish are kept, water flow should be unidirectional and only from eggs to grow-out fish, but can be recirculated within the specific fish production stage, and within the egg sector.	(free text note/comment)
<i>Biosecurity procedures</i>		
Separation of fish and controlled movement within the	<i>In production systems with an open seawater cycle,</i> different fish groups/age classes are kept in separate epidemiological units/sub-compartments with hygiene barriers	(free text note/comment)

establishment producing eggs/gametes	<p>between them to restrain and localise any infection that could occur in a tank. Before fish are moved from one unit to the next, it is recommended to check their health status. Tanks are washed and disinfected between movement of fish.</p> <p><i>In fresh-water only systems</i>, the only separation applied is between the sectors with eggs and those for grow-out of fish.</p> <p>In Recirculatory Aquaculture System (RAS), escaped fish living in the pipeline system, but outside the tanks, must be removed.</p>	(free text note/comment)
Origin of the broodfish	<p>Either from disinfected eyed eggs hatched at the establishment or establishments that comply with the same critical control points (at least with documented level of assurance of the health status of the population).</p> <p>Fish can also be introduced when originating from establishments in a zone or compartment that are officially free from the pathogens in question.</p>	(free text note/comment)
Quarantine of any introduced fish	<p><i>In production systems with an open seawater cycle</i>, new fish should be kept under observation for 4-8 weeks to detect clinical sign of disease, before being introduced to the main facility. Not relevant for <i>freshwater-only systems</i> (only officially disease-free are introduced).</p>	(free text note/comment)
Egg disinfection procedures	<p>Protocols used for green egg and eyed egg disinfection and their implementation should be well documented.</p>	(free text note/comment)
Compliance with biosecurity plan	<p>A quality assurance system with standard operating procedures and where critical operations are logged and documented needs to be implemented, i.e. RMMs.</p>	(free text note/comment)
Traceability	<p>Ensure there is a system in place to trace all movement of fish/eggs/gametes within and between establishments.</p>	(free text note/comment)
Fomites	<p>Separated for the different sectors within the establishment (including collection, storage and disposal of dead fish).</p> <p>Fomites are washed and disinfected regularly.</p>	(free text note/comment)
Personnel	<p>There should be requirements for personnel education/training.</p>	(free text note/comment)

	<p>All sectors within the establishment are entered by personnel through hygiene barriers with designated clothes and shoes.</p> <p>Ideally, personnel movement within a work day is unidirectional from eggs to fish though this may not always be possible. However, efficient hygiene barriers can mitigate the risk of virus transmission associated with movement of personnel.</p>	
Visitors	Keep records of any non-employees entering the farm, including service people and check whether they have visited other farms. Visitors enter through hygiene barriers with designated clothes and shoes.	(free text note/comment)
Disinfection of services	<p>Documentation of protocols and implementation of disinfection of vessels/trucks for transport, feed, etc.</p> <p>Measures to avoid spillage of water during loading and unloading should be taken.</p>	(free text note/comment)
Protecting establishment from access of birds and mammals	Additional biosecurity measures, such as protecting the establishment from access by birds and mammals (e.g. by wires and nets) would avoid these animals spreading the diseases	(free text note/comment)
<i>Diagnostic laboratory</i>		
Quality assurance and certification	Diagnostic laboratories should follow ISO 17025 standards	(free text note/comment)